

UNDERWATER DATALOGGER: A LOW-COST FLEXIBLE ARDUINO-BASED LOGGING PLATFORM

(Sistem Pengelogg Data Bawah Air)

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ABSTRACT

The work of underwater data logging and recording is one of an important process in which it is used to understand the physical chemistry and biological process occur underwater and one of the factors for the prediction of environmental issues. Students and the investigators who work in a water environment need a data logger for their further understandings. The underwater data loggers are usually used to log the data of temperature, pressure, light intensity, salinity, water cleanliness, chemical concentration and many more. All the data taken will be helpful to understand more about the condition of water. However, the current electronic underwater data logger in the market is overly priced even to carry out a small task and it has a very short lifespan. This is due to the underwater sensors are very sensitive and tend to get damage easily. Hence, the purpose of this project is to build a low-cost underwater data logger system. The system of this data logger is built by using Arduino Mega 2650 as the main brain of this system which connects with the other sensors like the sensor for temperature, water pressure, light intensity, salinity and the GPS sensor. All the data read from each sensor by the Arduino will be written on the MicroSD card with the aid of a MicroSD shield adapter. This system is capable of functioning 50m underwater with the aid of waterproof housing. In conclusion, the purpose of this project is to create a low-cost system of electronic underwater data logger through the Arduino board and sensors which capable to read and keep the data such as data for temperature, depth, light intensity, salinity and the location where the sample is taken.

Keywords: Arduino Mega 2650; Salinity; Depth; GPS; Light Intensity; Temperature

ABSTRAK

Kerja mengelogg atau merekod data parameter bawah air adalah suatu proses penting dijalankan dalam kajian untuk memahami fizikokimia, proses biologi yang berlaku dalam air dan ia merupakan faktor ramalan isu persekitaran. Pelajar dan penyelidik yang berkerja di persekitaran air dunia ini sering memerlukan pengeloggan data untuk pemahaman mereka. Pengelogg data bawah air selalunya mengelogg data parameter seperti suhu, tekanan, keamatan cahaya, kemasinan, kebersihan air, kepekatan kimia dan sebagainya. Segala data yang diambil akan menolong kita lebih memahami keadaan dan alam perairan tersebut. Namun demikian, pengelogg data elektronik bawah air yang sedia berkos tinggi walaupun untuk melakukan tugas yang kecil. Pengelogg data mempunyai jangka hayat yang pendek serta memerlukan perumah kalis air yang dapat menahan tekanan tinggi. Demikian kerana, penderia – penderia bawah air terlalu sensitif dan mudah mengalami kerosakan. Oleh itu, projek ini dijalankan dengan tujuan untuk membangunkan satu sistem pengelogg data bawah air yang berkos rendah. Sistem pengelogg data ini dibina dengan menggunakan Arduino Mega 2650 sebagai peranti pemproses utama yang diintegrasikan dengan penderia – penderia seperti sensor suhu, tekanan air, keamatan cahaya, kemasinan air dan penderia GPS. Segala bacaan penderia yang diambil oleh setiap penderia akan disimpan dalam kad memori MikroSD melalui papan Arduino dan penyesuai mikroSD. Sistem ini dianggarkan berupaya untuk berfungsi sedalam 50m bawah air dengan penolong perumah kalis air. Kesimpulannya, projek ini adalah untuk membangunkan sebuah sistem pengelogg data elektronik bawah air yang berkos rendah berdasarkan papan Arduino dan penderia – penderia yang berupaya untuk membaca dan menyimpan data seperti suhu, kedalaman, keamatan cahaya, kemasinan air dan juga lokasi sampel yang diambil.

Kata Kunci: Arduino Mega 2650; Kemasinan; Tekanan; GPS; Keamatan Cahaya; Suhu

INTRODUCTION

In this vast growing economy of modern and advance technology, it is very common to hear the term “data logging” as it plays a major role in many fields. Data logging is a process of recording data consistently for a period of time. Back in the old days data logging was done manual by relying on human for data collection. However, this process is time consuming and the probability of the data consisting of human error is relatively high. To overcome this problem engineers have invented the electronic data logger which is capable of collecting one or more data with a flexible sample rate and an adjustable recording period.

Underwater data logger is a data logger that is used by researchers and students working in the world rivers, lakes and oceans for their understanding about the environment. The most

common types of data collection done underwater are the temperature, salinity, light intensity, oxygen concentration, carbon dioxide concentration and etc.

The problem with todays modern underwater data logger is that it is overly priced even for a single data collector. The underwater data logger is also easily damaged and has a short lifespan of usage. Many studies in the past literature have focus on resolving this problem such as building a low-cost, data-logging salinity sensor (Pham et al. 2007). Another project was done entitled Cave Pearl Data Logger: A Flexible Arduino-Based Logging Platform for Long-Term Monitoring in Harsh Environments (Beddows & Mallon 2018). Figure 1 show the flow chart of the operational system of the Cave Pearl data logger project (Beddows & Mallon 2018).

FIGURE 1. Operational flow chart of the Cave Pearl project, (Beddows & Mallon 2018).

Another project was carried out to build an underwater temperature data logger using DS18B20 temperature sensor and Arduino (Dahoud & Fezari 2019). The temperature used in this project is low cost and it is capable of measuring the temperature accurately.

This aim of this project is to build a low-cost underwater data logger that is able to collect the temperature, salinity, light intensity, pressure, GPS position, date and time and store it in a MicroSD card. This project also aims to design a waterproof casing along with the brackets to hold the sensor in

the housing with the capability of being waterproof for up to 50m below water surface level.

METHODOLOGY

Experiment Design and Flow

The engineering methodology used in the project is the project is the engineering whereby the first process is to the problem analysis followed by the background studies then deciding the components used. Then the coding for the overall system is written. Once that is completed, the prototype is design and assembled the test run the device and followed by improvements or replacements.

The overall system is build using Arduino Mega 2560 as the microprocessor and integrated with the temperature sensor, light intensity sensor, pressure sensor, TDS sensor, GPS sensor and RTC module. Figure 2 shows the block diagram of the process in this project. The data from the sensors will be read by the Arduino and then written on the microSD card with the aid of a microSD shield adapter. Figure 3 shows the operational system flow of the underwater data logger that is designed.

FIGURE 2. Block diagram of the project flow

FIGURE 3. Operational system flow

Experiment Sensors Calibration

The sensors chosen for building this underwater data logging system was chosen based on a few different aspects. Firstly, the cost of the sensor was taken into place as one of the research objectives is to build a low-cost underwater data logger. Secondly, the specifications and the sensitivity of the sensors were taken into the aspects of choosing the sensors. Finally, the compatibility of the sensors with Arduino microprocessor was taken into place of choosing the sensor.

The temperature sensor that was chosen for this project is DS18B20 which has the capability to record temperature in the range of -55 °C to +125 °C with the accuracy up to ±0.01 °C. This sensor fits perfectly as the temperature of seawater is usually in between the range of -2 °C to +28 °C. As for the salinity sensors TDS meter V1.0 was chosen. Temt 6000 was chosen as the sensor to record the light intensity. As for the pressure sensor to determine the depth position of the data logger, MS5540CM was

chosen. Figure 4 shows the image of all the sensors chosen for this project, along with the flow of the data.

FIGURE 4. Image of overall sensors connection

All the sensors were calibrated separately to ensure that the quality of the output data by the sensors are reliable. The methods of calibrating each sensor are different. The temperature sensor DS18B20 was calibrated by comparing sensor reading with the reading of a mercury thermometer. The range of test run done was from 2 °C to +80 °C with an interval of 3 °C. Figure 5 shows the image of the calibration being done.

FIGURE 4. Temperature sensor calibration process

The light ambient sensor was also calibrated by comparing the reading from temt6000 sensor and the reading gotten from the “Lux Light Meter” application. This application can be downloaded from Google Play Store. The measurement of light ambience is called LUX. As the light intensity hitting on the sensors increase the value of the LUX will increase. A light source is placed 50 cm away and the distance was varied by an interval of 2 cm. Figure 5 shows the image of the calibration being done.

FIGURE 5. Ambient sensor calibration process

The TDS sensor data was calibrated by observing the readings gradual increment as 5 ml of 0.04 ml/g concentrated saline was added in 500ml of tap water that was kept a constant room temperature. The measurement of this was recorded in PPM which stands for parts per million. Figure 6 shows the process of calibrating the TDS sensor.

FIGURE 6. TDS sensor calibration process

As for the GPS sensor, the longitude and latitude data is compared with the data from Google Maps. This process was repeated with 3 different locations. The pressure sensor was calibrated by observing the increment in the output data as the sensor is submerged in to different depth of water.

Waterproof Housing Design

This system is design to be waterproof up to 50m below water surface level. Therefore, a waterproof housing is designed. The design also includes brackets to hold the components in the housing. A transparent acrylic plexiglass tube with the thickness of 5mm and a diameter of 105mm was used as the casing. Figure 7 shows the image of the housing used.

FIGURE 7. Acrylic plexiglass tube

As for the end caps, it was designed with the aid of an online platform called OnShape. The brackets for each sensor were also designed using the same platform. This is designed to be 3D printed using a 3D printer. The end caps are design to be fitted with silicon-O ring to prevent the water from entering the housing. Figure 8 shows the complete 3D drawing of the bottom cap along with the brackets to hold the sensors in the waterproof housing and figure 9 shows the 3D complete drawing of the top cap.

FIGURE 8. 3D drawing of bottom end cap and brackets

FIGURE 9. 3D drawing of top end cap

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of Sensor Calibration

All the sensors were calibrated separately before the integration of all the sensors and Arduino was done. Table 1 shows the data collected for the calibration process of the DS18B20 temperature sensor. Table 1 show the data collected by the DS18B20 and the data collected using the mercury thermometer along with the difference between both of the data. Figure 10 shows the graph obtained from the calibration process. Based on the graph, it can be concluded that the reading from the DS18B20 temperature sensor is accurate and reliable.

FIGURE 10. Graph of DS18B20 temperature calibration process

TABLE 1. Data of DS18B20 temperature sensor calibration

No. of Reading	Temperature Reading (°C)		
	Thermometer	DS18B20 sensor	Temperature Difference
1	2.00	2.39	-0.39
2	5.00	5.00	+0.00
3	8.00	7.59	+0.41
4	11.00	11.35	-0.35
5	14.00	14.43	-0.43
6	17.00	17.00	0.00
7	20.00	19.79	+0.21
8	23.00	22.57	+0.43
9	26.00	26.39	-0.39
10	29.00	28.50	+0.50
11	32.00	32.19	-0.19
12	35.00	34.80	+0.20
13	38.00	38.19	-0.19
14	41.00	41.75	-0.75
15	44.00	44.87	-0.87
16	47.00	46.87	+0.13
17	50.00	50.00	+0.00
18	53.00	52.89	+0.11
19	56.00	55.90	+0.10
20	59.00	59.67	-0.67
21	62.00	61.28	+0.72
22	65.00	64.00	+1.00
23	68.00	67.79	+0.21
24	71.00	71.68	-0.68
25	74.00	74.19	-0.19
26	77.00	76.63	+0.37
27	80.00	81.00	-1.00

As for the light ambient sensor calibration, the readings of the TEmT600 was compared with the reading from the application. Figure 11 shows the graph of the both

readings. Table 2 shows the data obtained from the calibration process

FIGURE 10. Graph of TEMT6000 light ambient sensor calibration

TABLE 2. Data of TEMT 6000 light ambient sensor calibration

Distance from light source and sensors (cm)	Readings of TEMT6000 (LUX)	Readings from the Application (LUX)
50	0	1
48	2	3
46	4	4
44	5	6
42	7	8
40	9	9
38	11	11
36	16	15
34	23	21
32	31	31
30	37	38
28	49	49
26	64	66
24	77	75
22	87	90
20	122	99
18	111	111
16	119	120
14	129	129
12	139	137
10	180	176

Figure 11 shows the data of calibrating the TDS sensor. This calibration process was done by observing the value of data increment as the salinity

of the tap water was increased by adding saline in to it. Table 3 shows the data of TDS sensors calibration.

FIGURE 11. Graph of TDS sensor calibration

TABLE 2. Data of TEMT 6000 light ambient sensor calibration

Concentrated (0.04 g/ml) salt water (ml)	TDS sensor reading (PPM)
0	51
5	181
10	351
15	501
20	667
25	867
30	1017
35	1107
40	1197
45	1236
50	1236

In short, all the sensors were calibrated before the system integration was done. Based on the calibration done all the sensors used are capable of outputting reliable data for the underwater data logger.

Serial Communication Between Arduino and The Sensors

Once all the sensors were calibrated, the sensors were integrated with the Arduino and microSD

shield adapter. An Arduino coding was written for this integration. The sensors were assembled with the Arduino with a series of wire connection. Figure 12 show the complete wiring diagram of the integration between all the sensors and Arduino.

The coding written for the integration of the system allows the Arduino Mega 2560 to read the output data from all the sensors simultaneously and allows to data to be written on the microSD card which can be opened on any compatible devices.

FIGURE 12. Schematic wiring diagram of the integration between all the components

Waterproof Housing

The waterproof housing for this underwater data logging system is expected to be waterproof up to 50m. The material used for casing of the waterproof housing is a clear acrylic plexiglass tube with the thickness of 5mm. This material has a tensile strength up to 75 MPA. Which means it can withstand the water pressure up to 7 KM below

water surface level. The endcaps were design on the online platform, OnShape 3D. However, due to the current pandemic the end caps and brackets for the housing were unable to be 3D printed. Figure 13 shows the complete 3D drawing of the waterproof housing. The waterproof housing is very durable and compact as it is estimated to be 300 mm tall and has a diameter of 105 mm.

FIGURE 13. 3D drawing of the waterproof housing

Overall underwater data logging system result

This system is capable of logging the data of underwater temperature, salinity, light intensity, pressure, GPS position, time and date. The data that

is logged will be written on a microSD card which can be removed from the system.

In this study, the system is battery powered by using a rechargeable LiPo battery with the capacitance of 1500 mAh. This battery is able to powerup the system for a time period of 12 hours in a single full charge.

There are two modes of initiation for the system to start logging the first mode also known as the manual start up is starting the system by clicking the toggle button. Clicking the button again will send the system into stand-by mode. The second mode of initiation is called the automatic start up, whereby as soon as the value of the TDS sensor is not equal to zero, the system will start writing the logged data on the microSD card.

The system also consists of LED indications to notify the current operation of the system. Red indicated that there is the problem in the system. Yellow light indicates that the system is on standby mode and ready to log the data on the microSD card and finally the green light indicates that the system is running and the data is being written on the microSD card real-time.

Figure 14 shows the image of the overall

system with the sensors, microprocessor and battery.

FIGURE 14. Overall data logging system

Figure 15 shows the sample output data that is written on the microSD card. The data is saved on a .txt format so that it can be easily transfer to Microsoft Excel for further understanding.

FIGURE 15. Output from the data logging system

Figure 16 shows the position of the sensors and microprocessor in the designed bracket. The

brackets were also unable to be 3D printed due to the arise of the 2020 pandemic.

FIGURE 16. Position of the components in the designed bracket

CONCLUSION

In this project, a fully functional underwater data logging system was built. This system is capable of logging the temperature, salinity, light intensity, pressure, GPS position, time and date. This system is able to log and stored the data on a removeable microSD card. The system has a flexible data collection sample rate from as low as 1 second interval up to as long as desired by the user. This system is battery operated and can run for 12 hours

with a single full charge. In addition, the system also has a LED light indication function to notify the user when the system is running, on standby or faulty.

In this project also a waterproof housing was designed with the capability of being waterproof up to 50 m below water surface level. The casing for the design uses clear acrylic plexiglass tube with the thickness of 5mm. The end caps and brackets were successfully design by using the online platform, OnShape 3D. However, due to the current pandemic the end caps and brackets we unable to be 3D printed.

My suggestion for the further improvement of the projects are to add a Bluetooth or Wi-Fi module so that the data can be obtained without removing the endcaps as this method will cause wear and tear. Secondly, building an application to control the systems operation and setting the time period of data collection will also be a good improvement.

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